

Current Status: ALPHA (Stage 2/3)

The current status of the project is that Stage 2 is *ideally* completed and Stage 3 is about to commence (Table 1). Table 2 outlines the timetable for the project.

Table 1: Data provided at each stage.

Stage	Forcing data	Built and veg. cover %	Urban morphology details	Details of Urban Materials
1	✓			
1.5	✓	✓		
2	✓	✓	✓	
3	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2: Planned timetable

Target date	Objective	Status
1 Mar	Outputs of test data returned	Complete
1 April	First dataset released (Stage 1)	Complete
30 April	Deadline for return of Stage 1 output	On-going
1 May	Land cover data issued (Stage 1.5)*	On-going
31 May	Deadline for return of Stage 1.5 output	On-going
1 June	Urban morph. data issued (Stage 2)*	On-going
30 June	Deadline for return of Stage 2 output	On-going
1 July	Urban materials data issued (Stage 3)	On-going
1 Aug	All site data released (Stage 4)	

* Note: subsequent data only released following receipt of output from the previous Stage.

The current status for all participants is given in Table 3. If you have yet to return your data to us *please do so as soon as possible*. Modelling groups will not receive data for subsequent stages without our receiving output (model results, parameter values used, timestamp) from the previous stage. Please check Table 3 and make us aware of any potential inaccuracies.

For stage 3, participants will be issued with detailed information regarding the materials of the site and their characteristics for use in their model. This data will be issued in due course.

AMS Annual Meeting, January 2009, Phoenix, AZ.

The initial results of this work are to be presented at the AMS Annual Meeting in 2009 with the theme: "Urban Weather and Climate: Now and the Future" <http://www.ametsoc.org/MEET/annual>>. Depending on interest, we may also want to consider a dedicated session at this meeting. Abstracts are due on 1 August. Please email Sue.Grimmond@kcl.ac.uk **as soon as possible** if you would be interested in participating in such a session.

Initial Parameter Survey from Stage 0 (VL92)

The remainder of this newsletter consists are the results of a survey of the parameter values utilised by each modelling group in Stage 0 of this project. In this survey models are referred to by model number to ensure their anonymity. Each group should be aware of their specific identifier although if you are unsure, please contact us. Also, if you see *any problems* with the parameters plotted for your model, please let us know.

The following Figures depict the parameter variables returned. In all cases, the parameter values are plotted against model identifier number.

It will be evident that for many models there are no parameter values. This may be because the model itself does not consider this value or because we were not made aware of it. It is imperative that we understand all parameters that were assumed at this stage. It will also be evident that in some cases, values plotted are unrealistic, with surface cover proportions of >100% for example.

If you have not checked the output that we sent you last month please can you look through it. We would like all groups to confirm their agreement of the plots for this and last month. In particular from the last month the **timestamp** needs to be confirmed. For this month, it is clear that some models have default values that have not been reported for their parameters. **Please can you email an updated version of your parameters spreadsheet.**

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Figure 1: Albedo values used by each model (Stage 0)

Figure 2: Emissivity values used by each model (Stage 0)

Figure 3: Fractions of land cover used by each model (Stage 0).

Figure 4: Fractions of land cover assumed as parameters for each model examined, plotted as the sum proportion (Stage 0. *These models detail additional surface fractions although the details of these are unclear.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivity values used (Stage 0).

Figure 6: Volumetric heat capacity values used (Stage 0).

Figure 7: Temperatures values used as parameters (Stage 0).

Figure 8: Heights used (Stage 0).

Figure 9: Roughness and zero plane displacement length for momentum (Stage 0).

Figure 10: Material roughness length for momentum values (Stage 0).

Figure 11: Roughness length for heat values used (Stage 0).

Table 3: Groups participating and their current status

Model	Test data verified?*	Test data parameters received?	Data for Stage 1 received?	Stage 1 parameters received?	Stage 1.5 data returned?	Stage 1.5 Parameters returned?	Stage 2 data returned?	Stage 2 parameters returned?
11		✓	✓	✓				
12		✓	✓		Data not released	-	-	-
13					Data not released	-	-	-
14	✓		Data not released	-	-	-	-	-
15			Data not released	-	-	-	-	-
16		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
17		✓			Data not released	-	-	-
18			Data not released	-	-	-	-	-
20			Data not released	-	-	-	-	-
21		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
22		✓			-	-	-	-
25		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
26			Data not released	-	-	-	-	-
28		✓	✓	✓				
30		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
31		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
32		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
33		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
35	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
36		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
37					Data not released	-	-	-
39		✓	✓	✓				
41		✓			Data not released	-	-	-
42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
43	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
46		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
47		✓	✓	✓			Data not released	-
49		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
50		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

*verified refers to whether or not we have had the accuracy of plots distributed for each mode, confirmed by the participant.

This project contributes to:

General FAQs

What is this project about?

Please see the documents at:

www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

What are the first steps required to join the model comparison?

If you would like to participate then please contact us at:

UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

Will there be a second or third round?

It is hoped that there will be a second and potentially a third round of comparison, each using a different set of forcing data. This of course, depends on data availability and on the success of the first round. It is important to realise that success of this

project depends on the commitment of all participants and their meeting the specified deadlines.

Will I be told of the performance of my model?

Yes – individual groups will be informed but only on the status of their particular model(s). Overall results will be published but models will be referred to by code known only to that participant and the project coordinators.

I have queries specific to Round 1/ALPHA.

Please refer to the ALPHA data FAQs which can be found at the end of this newsletter or contact us at: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

Urban Model Comparison ALPHA Data FAQs

Where can I get the ALPHA data from?

If you are a confirmed participant, the evaluation data will be sent to you in either (or both) and ASCII or netCDF format. The file containing the data is called ALPHA. If you have not received the data or if you would like it to be resent, please contact us at: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

I cannot read the dataset

If this happens it may be that you are examining either the netCDF or ASCII file believing it to be the other. If you are still unable to view the data then please email and we will endeavour to help you.

What does the ALPHA dataset consist of?

At Stage 1, the content of the forcing data only consists of the following variables:

- Year – the year of the data (either 1 or 2)
- DecTime - decimal time
- Day – day of year in format 1-365
- Time – hour of day in 24-hour format
- SWdown – incoming shortwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)
- LWdown – downwelling longwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)
- Wind_N – northward, v, wind component ($m s^{-1}$)
- Wind_E – eastward, u, wind component ($m s^{-1}$)
- PSurf – station pressure (Pa)
- Tair – air temperature (K)
- Qair – specific humidity ($kg kg^{-1}$)
- Rainf – rainfall rate ($kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$)

Where possible, these variables meet the ALMA convention in terms of naming and units, although where this has not been possible, new naming conventions have been adopted.

What is the ALMA convention?

ALMA stands for: Assistance for Land-surface Modelling Activities (ALMA) convention was developed to facilitate exchange of forcing data for land-surface schemes and their results. See: <http://www.lmd.jussieu.fr/~polcher/ALMA/>

Should all variables in the test data be used?

Not necessarily – if your model does not need all the data then do not use it.

Should the whole timeseries of data be used? Yes.

What are averaging periods for the data?

The data are half-hourly averaged values for the time ending i.e. 10:30 is 10:01 to 10:30. Your data should be half-hourly averaged for this time period and should not be a sample/instantaneous value on the half-hour.

What time-zone should be assumed?

Please use the time within the test file (i.e. local time).

I need latitude and longitude

If you need these details then please assume the following location: 37.7308 °S, 65.014 °W

Does the ALPHA dataset contain filled gaps?

Yes it does. Details of the gaps filled and methods used to complete it can be found within the ALPHA file.

Are there any data available for model “spin up”?

If you need this we will assume the first ~ 100 days of data are spin up (they will be analysed separately). However, you must still provide the output for all time periods.

I do not need “spin-up” data.

In this case, please simply use the whole ALPHA dataset with your model.

What are the temporal and spatial scales to be modelled?

Spatial: the model output should be for a point that is at the equivalent of the first layer in a meso-scale model or at the blending height. i.e. it is local scale (spatially integrated for a neighbourhood) as are the observations. It should not be a microscale result for a point within the canyon.

The forcing data and the observations which the models, will be compared to, were taken at:

6.25 x mean roughness height

Temporal: The model results will be compared on a 30-minute time scale (and longer). These will be the average for the 30-minute period and are for the half-hourly ending time stamp.

What values should I used as parameters for my model?

At this stage in the project no parameter values will be given to you. Where these are required you are to make “sensible assumptions” based on the fact that the data were obtained from within a city. If you feel this is not possible please contact us to discuss.

What more can we know about the ALPHA data?

At this stage we can tell you no more about the site at which this data were collected. If you require details of any other parameters you will need to assume these.

What data should I return?

- 1) Model results for the full period (see Table 4 for more details).
- 2) Parameter values used/assumed in spreadsheet provided.
- 3) Spin up procedure (if applicable).
- 4) Height which model results are for.
- 5) Metadata which explains you model results (column labels, definition, units).

Table 4 lists the minimum output variables that we need returned at each stage, along with the associated name and units according to the ALMA convention.

Table 4: Minimum data to be returned, where there is no ALMA convention, please use these names and units.

Variable	ALMA Name	ALMA Units
Upwelling short-wave radiation	SWup	W m ⁻²
Upwelling long-wave radiation	LWup	W m ⁻²
Net all-wave radiation	Qnet	W m ⁻²
Sensible heat flux	Qh	W m ⁻²
Latent heat flux	Qle	W m ⁻²
Storage heat flux	Qstor	W m ⁻²
Momentum flux [†]	Qtau	N m ⁻²

Anthropogenic heat flux [†]	Qanth	W m ⁻²
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† optional variables – if your model output these data

In what format should the model outputs be returned?

1. We will accept data in ASCII format or netCDF files. Please ensure the format of your data matches that which you returned to us in the test phase. If the format will differ then please let us know.
2. When submitting your output please include a metadata file with the format of your data and the units used.
3. We need to know the parameter values you chose.
4. Ideally your output file will be formatted in the same way as the ALPHA netCDF or ASCII file and will use ALMA conventions (or our specific conventions).

Do I need to tell you what parameters I have used in implementing my model?

Yes – this is important. If you have not received a form for collecting this information then please contact us. We require this information as soon as possible. Note that a copy of this form is required for each stage ie. for each run of your model.

What constitutes satisfactory data?

This means that we are able to access and analyse the data and that the other details requested are provided. Also, that the data returned to us should meet the ALMA conventions as closely as possible.

What stages does the project consist of?

The project will consist of five stages. The data that will be provided at each stage are:

- Stage 1 – only forcing variables
- Stage 1.5- built and vegetation cover (as a percentage)
- Stage 2 - morphology data
- Stage 3 –materials data
- Stage 4 –entire evaluation dataset

Note that for all stages the same forcing data (alpha) are to be used, however you will be provided with more information regarding the site at each stage allowing you to more realistically assign parameter values and reduce other assumptions.

Can I receive all data at once?

No. You will only receive data for the following Stage after returning output from the previous stage.

What is the timetable of the whole project?

We would like the output of your models to be returned to us as soon as possible and within a month ideally. Table 5 shows a timetable of the project.

Table 5: Timetable of project

Data Set	Round	Stage	Comments
VL92	0	0	Complete
ALPHA	1	1	Data distributed 1 April
		1	Output returned 30 April
		1.5	Data distributed 1 May

	1.5	Output returned 31 May
	2	Data distributed 1 June
	2	Output returned 30 June
	3	Data distributed 1 July
	4	Data distributed 1 August

Will I automatically receive the data for each stage?

No – you will only receive data for the following stage when you return the output from the previous stage to us and we find it satisfactory.

Can I distribute the data I am sent (neither the VL92 data nor the evaluation data) or use it for another purpose?

No – the data we send you is for use by you on this project only. We ask you to agree to this by participating in this work. Any

data we send must also not be exchanged among participants as you may be at a different stage in the project.

What if I have more questions?

Please email UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk with any further queries and we will respond as quickly as possible.

Funding provided by:

Met Office

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